

**glycan
trigger**

D6.3 – Development and update of the Data Management Plan 2

WP6

Date: 02 12 2024

Funded by
the European Union

DOCUMENT CONTROL SHEET

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Number	101093997		
Project Acronym	GlycanTrigger		
Project Full title	Glycans as master triggers of health to intestinal inflammation transition		
Project Start Date	1 January 2023		
Project Duration	72 months		
Funding Instrument	Horizon Europe	Funding Scheme	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-02-01		
Coordinator	Salomé Pinho (i3S), salomep@i3s.up.pt		

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable No	
Deliverable Title	Development and update of the Data Management Plan 2
Work-Package No	WP6
Work-Package Title	Project management
WP-Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Salomé Pinho (i3S)
Task No	6.2
Task Title	Ethics and data management and gender equality
Task Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Salomé Pinho (i3S)
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Other Authors (Name and Short Org. Name)	Salomé Pinho (i3S)
Reviewers (Name and Short Org. Name)	Salomé Pinho (i3S)
Status	Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Deliverable Type	Report <input type="checkbox"/> Data <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/> Data Management Plan <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Dissemination Level	Public (PU) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sensitive (SEN) <input type="checkbox"/> Classified <input type="checkbox"/> PU: Public, fully open SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

DOCUMENT VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
1	21/10/2024	Vanda Pinto	1 st Draft
2	11/10/2024	Vanda Pinto	Contributions from work package leaders, partners, and team members

DOCUMENT REVIEW

Reviewer	Date	Reviewer Name (Short Organisation Name)
1	20/11/2024	Salomé Pinho (i3S)
2	29/11/2024	Salomé Pinho (i3S)

Legal disclaimer

This project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101093997. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
CD	Crohn's disease
DMP	Data Management Plan
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IBD	Inflammatory bowel disease
NAS	Network-Attached Storage
NDAs	Non-Disclosure Agreements
RIA	Research and Innovation Actions
WP	Work Package
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable

Table of contents

About the project.....	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Data Summary	9
2. FAIR data	16
2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	16
2.2 Making data accessible.....	17
2.3 Making data interoperable.....	19
2.4 Increase data re-use	19
3. Other research outputs.....	21
4. Allocation of resources.....	23
5. Data security.....	25
6. Ethical aspects	27
7. Other issues	29
8. Conclusion.....	31

About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health-to-chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and lifestyle to maintain a healthy gut.

Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

Partners:

Short name	Legal name
I3S (Coordinator)	I3S - INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (Portugal)
LUMC	ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN (The Netherlands)
SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ (France)
CHARITE	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETSMEDIZIN BERLIN (Germany)
GLSMED LH	GLSMED LEARNING HEALTH SA (Portugal)
MOUNT SINAI	ICAHN SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AT MOUNT SINAI (USA)
EFCCA	EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF CROHN'S AND ULCERATIVE COLITIS ASSOCIATIONS (Belgium)
SPI	SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACÃO CONSULTADORIA EMPRESARIAL E FOMENTO DA INOVACÃO SA (Portugal)
LUD	LUDGER LIMITED (United Kingdom)

Executive Summary

The **D6.3 – Development and update of the Data Management Plan 2** deliverable presents the updated version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the GlycanTrigger project, building on the initial DMP by incorporating the practical implementation and ongoing oversight of data management practices since the start of the project. This version continues to provide an overview of the data generated and curated in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Open Science policies, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, ensuring that data is as open as possible and as closed as necessary.

Throughout the past year, each work package (WP) has actively managed data following the specifications laid out in the initial DMP. This updated DMP provides a summary of collected data to date, with confirmation that data storage, documentation, metadata standards, and data security protocols are consistent with the original plan. Minor adjustments to data management, as informed by practical experience, are also noted to enhance data quality and security.

All partners continue to document their data handling procedures in accordance with GlycanTrigger's data management framework. Data governance remains under the stewardship of i3S, which performs periodic reviews to ensure compliance and updates, with support from the i3S units on Responsible Conduct in Research and the Data Protection Unit. These periodic reviews reinforce GlycanTrigger's commitment to ethical and responsible data handling, reflecting feedback from both internal and external evaluations.

This second version demonstrates GlycanTrigger's adherence to the Horizon Europe data management standards and reaffirms that the DMP is a dynamic document, to be periodically assessed and refined as the project progresses.

Chapter 1

Data Summary

1. Data Summary

The GlycanTrigger project continues to generate a diverse array of data through its scientific methodologies and dissemination activities, with contributions from all project partners. As the project has progressed, each WP leader has implemented data management strategies based on the initial specifications, ensuring consistent data collection, storage, and documentation.

In this updated Data Summary, we present refined tables that include details on the types of data collected to date. This updated summary reflects the actual data and metadata structures, which have been applied across WPs as part of our commitment to standardized, high-quality data management practices. These tables reflect our current approach and will be updated as needed in future versions of the DMP to incorporate ongoing project developments.

WP 1- Mapping the gut mucosa glycome in health-to-inflammation transition	
Lead Beneficiary: LUMC	
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	This WP will generate data related with the structural characterization of the gut glycome composition as well as the glyco-immune transcriptomic profile from health to gut inflammation transition.
What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data from the following methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mass spectrometry imaging (.imzML;.ibd; .ome; .tiff) -Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry in negative ion mode (.mzXML) -Mass Cytometry Imaging (CyTOF) (.mcd; .txt) -Spatial transcriptomics (.csv) -Tissue (immune)histochemistry (.tiff; .jpeg) -quantitative PCR analysis (.csv) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical analysis (to be determined) • Documents (.docx; .pptx; .pdf) and images (.png; .tiff; .jpeg)
Will you re-use any existing data and how?	To be determined.
What is the origin of the data?	Data will be generated from the analysis of samples derived from patients with CD and healthy controls.
What is the expected size of the data?	>1 TB
To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	The data may be useful for some partners of the GlycanTrigger consortium and for the scientific community in general.

WP 2 - Understanding the biological impact of changes in gut glycome in microbial and immunological dynamics

Lead Beneficiary: SORBONNE

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	This WP will generate data from the analysis of how the mucosa glycosylation signature in CD patients changes the composition and function of the microbiome. In addition, the impact of the gut glycome in metabolomics and immunological dynamics associated with gut inflammation will be analysed.
What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data from the following methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -shotgun metagenomics sequencing (to be determined) -16S rRNA sequencing (.tsv) -Correlation analysis (.csv) -LC-MS for metabolomics (to be determined) -FACS (.FCS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical analysis (to be determined) • Documents (.docx; .pptx; .pdf) and images (.png; .tiff; .jpeg)
Will you re-use any existing data and how?	To be determined.
What is the origin of the data?	Data will be generated from the analysis of human and mouse tissue and stool samples.
What is the expected size of the data?	>1 TB
To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	The data may be useful for some partners of the GlycanTrigger consortium and for the scientific community in general.

WP 3 - Unravelling the cellular and molecular mechanisms of how changes in gut glycosylation activate innate and humoral immune responses

Lead Beneficiary: i3S

<p>What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>	<p>This WP will generate different types of data from the analysis of the impact of changes in gut glycosylation in the cellular and molecular mechanisms associated with the activation of both innate and humoral immune responses.</p>
<p>What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data from the following methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Cytometric bead array (.FCS) -FACS (.FCS) -ELISA (.csv) -LC-ESI-MS (.raw, .mzXML) -Single cell sorting (.FCS) -BCR sequencing (.seq) • Statistical analysis (.xlsx; .cvs;.PZF) • Documents (.docx; .pptx; .pdf) and images (.png; .tiff; .jpeg) • Educational data will essentially consist of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Presentation slides (.ppt or .pdf) -Seminar video recordings (.mp4) -Scientific posters (.ppt or .pdf) -Scientific handbooks (.pdf or paper) -Publications (.pdf)
<p>Will you re-use any existing data and how?</p>	<p>Data from literature, public databases, and from GlycanTrigger partners.</p>
<p>What is the origin of the data?</p>	<p>The data will be collected/generated in the laboratory from the measurements of the samples from different animal models developed in the context of this project, as well as from serum samples derived from patients with CD and healthy controls.</p>
<p>What is the expected size of the data?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data >1Tb • Statistical analysis <1Gb • Documents and images <1Tb
<p>To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?</p>	<p>The data will be important for some partners of the GlycanTrigger consortium such as the coordinator (i3S) and participant partners (LUMC, Charité, GLSMED LH, Mount Sinai, LUD) and useful for the scientific community in general.</p>

WP 4 - Therapeutic efficacy of glyco-metabolic remodeling in preventing health-to-inflammation transition: the proof of concept

Lead Beneficiary: GLSMED LH

<p>What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>	<p>Data will be collected on the effects (clinical, endoscopic and immunological) of glycan supplementation both in mouse models and in humans.</p>
<p>What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data from the following methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lectin histochemistry (.tiff; .jpeg) -FACS (.FCS) -shotgun metagenomics sequencing (to be determined) -LC-MS for metabolomics (to be determined) -CBA (.FCS) -ELISA (.csv) • Patient data: demographics, sex/gender and disease related information such as disease location, phenotype, duration, prior medications, reason for surgery, and smoking status (.docx) • Patient data on clinical (Harvey-Bradshaw index - HBI; endoscopic postoperative recurrence rate – POR (defined by the Rutgeerts score), biochemical parameters (Calprotectin; CRP, Hemoglobin) and adverse events • Data from informed consent forms (.docx; .pdf) • Data from clinical questionnaires (.docx) • Statistical analysis (to be determined) • Documents (.docx; .pptx; .pdf) and images (.png; .tiff; .jpeg) • Educational data will essentially consist of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Presentation slides (.ppt or .pdf) -Seminar video recordings (.mp4) -Scientific posters (.ppt or .pdf) -Publications (.pdf)
<p>Will you re-use any existing data and how?</p>	<p>All data will be collected prospectively.</p>
<p>What is the origin of the data?</p>	<p>Data will be collected prospectively from patients.</p>
<p>What is the expected size of the data?</p>	<p>Data on approximately 60 patients (30 with glycan and 30 without supplementation) will be collected.</p>
<p>To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?</p>	<p>The data will be important for all consortium and for the CD patients, with the possibility to understand the mechanism of health-to-inflammation transition.</p>

WP 5 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication

Lead Beneficiary: SPI

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The datasets of WP5 contain information related to the project dissemination and exploitation.
What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template and reporting documents (.docx; .pptx; .xlsx) • Visual materials and Images/Photographs (.png; .tiff; .jpeg) • Video and podcast recordings (.mp4; .mp3) • Press-releases, brochures, flyers, roll-ups and poster/Infographics (.pdf) • Newsletters (.html)
Will you re-use any existing data and how?	Data from literature and public databases to produce informative and educational communication content, and from GlycanTrigger partners to communicate and disseminate the project activities.
What is the origin of the data?	Data will be collected throughout the lifecycle of the project from internal project developments, literature reviews, public databases, and partner contributions.
What is the expected size of the data?	<1Tb
To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	Partners and all target groups of the project.

WP 6 - Project management	
Lead Beneficiary: i3S	
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The data collected in WP6 contains information related to the project management and coordination.
What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detailed consortium contact information (.xlsx) • Photographs/images (.png; .tiff; .jpeg) will be collected and processed in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) will be used to protect confidential information from unauthorized disclosure. Consent forms will be obtained from individuals whose personal data will be used in the project, including photographs/images, to ensure informed consent and compliance with data protection regulations (.docx; .pdf) • A dataset containing the identified risks from the beginning of the project accompanied with the mitigation plans (.docx), as already detailed in D6.1 Risk Assessment Analysis • Financial information of each partner of the consortium will be included in a dataset (.xlsx)
Will you re-use any existing data and how?	The re-use of any existing data shall be limited to the project consortium members and the European Commission's Services.
What is the origin of the data?	Data will be collected throughout the lifecycle of the project.
What is the expected size of the data?	<1Tb
To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	All partners and the European Commission.

Chapter 2

FAIR data

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Since the initial DMP, GlycanTrigger has actively implemented the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles in ongoing data collection and management. To date, project data has been organized according to these standards, with metadata generated and stored in line with interoperability guidelines. Data that has been collected and finalized, where applicable, is also being prepared for open access in alignment with these principles.

As described previously, the Glycan Trigger project is committed to the following underlying principles to facilitate the discoverability, accessibility, dissemination and reusability of the project data:

- Persistent identifiers will be assigned to the shared data and included in its metadata, so to make data findable;
- Detailed documentation on the datasets will be provided, with metadata being based on standard vocabulary(ies), whenever possible, making data accessible;
- Standardized methodologies and metadata content will be aimed, in order to make data interoperable;
- The relevant data collected in the course of the project, except sensitive and personal data, will be made openly available, with respect to possible embargo periods, through data repositories and with suitable licenses, thus making data re-usable.

When disclosing product information before publication, external researchers or collaborators will be requested to sign Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) to maintain intellectual property protected.

Data documentation within GlycanTrigger will include:

- A description of the data itself: the overview of the files generated from a specific dataset will be included in a readme file, with the data format, the software used to read the data, and a description of the codes and variables used and their significance.
- A description of the data collection process and the tools used: this will include instruments such as codebooks, lab journals, logbooks, diaries, questionnaires, and manuals.
- A description of the changes of the dataset over time: a so-called historical report of the wanderings and processing of the research data in time is necessary to understand the origin of the data.

- As a convention, in GlycanTrigger, the following file name structure will be adopted: (research output) context_ yyyy.mm.dd_creator initials_version.extension

Technical metadata created will be automatically generated by the equipment used. This is based on the date/time and specifications of the captured data.

For glycomics and glycotranscriptomics/genetic data, we will follow the requirements given by EGA (European Genome-phenome Archive). Common field-specific standard formats will be used, such as mzXML, mzML, imzML and fastq. Field-specific guidelines, such as the MIRAGE standard (Minimum Information Required About a Glycomics Experiment), will provide guidance as to the completeness of metadata.

For proteomics raw data, supporting information and/or documentation will be provided according to the standards of the data repository, for example, MassIVE (<https://massive.ucsd.edu/ProteoSAFe/static/massive.jsp?redirect=auth>).

Additionally, we will provide extensive protocols in the form of peer-reviewed publications, such as research articles, protocols or data descriptors. These will contain the following information: a DOI, essential protocols or references to publicly available versions, processed data, figures, and a final pdf version of the manuscript.

2.2 Making data accessible

Specifically, processed and curated scientific data such as manuscripts, protocols, reviews and book chapters will be made available, after clearance for public dissemination, by publishing this data in golden open access journals/books. When this is not possible, we will use green open access. If necessary, we will use Sherpa/Romeo (<https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>) to check if the selected publisher allows self-archiving and corresponding embargo periods.

For green open access, we will use Open Science repositories. In detail:

- Manuscripts, reviews, reports and book chapters will be deposited in the institutional repository available at the University of Porto (<https://repositorio-aberto.up.pt/>) or in preprint servers such as bioRxiv (<https://www.biorxiv.org/>) or MedRxiv (<https://www.medrxiv.org/>).

To date, the project has deposited **six peer-reviewed publications** in the Open Repository of the University of Porto, ensuring open access availability and compliance with FAIR principles. Metadata for each publication was prepared using standardized formats to enhance findability and interoperability.

List of publications:

Vicente, M. M., Alves, I., et al. (2023). Mannosylated glycans impair normal T-cell development by reprogramming commitment and repertoire diversity. *Cellular & Molecular Immunology*, 20(8), 955-968. DOI: 10.1038/s41423-023-01052-7

Vicente, M. M., et al. (2023). Glycome dynamics in T and B cell development: basic immunological mechanisms and clinical applications. *Trends in Immunology*, 40 (8), 585-597. DOI: 10.1016/j.it.2023.06.004

Pinho, S. S., et al. (2023). Immune regulatory networks coordinated by glycans and glycan-binding proteins in autoimmunity and infection. *Cellular & Molecular Immunology*, 20(10), 1101-1113. DOI: 10.1038/s41423-023-01074-1

Gaifem J, et al. (2024) A unique serum IgG glycosylation signature predicts development of Crohn's disease and is associated with pathogenic antibodies to mannose glycan. *Nature Immunology*, 25(9):1692-1703. DOI: 10.1038/s41590-024-01916-8

Almeida P, et al. (2024) Glycans in Trained Immunity: Educators of innate immune memory in homeostasis and disease. *Carbohydrate Research*, 544:109245. DOI: 10.1016/j.carres.2024.109245

Crouch LI, et al. (2024) The role of glycans in health and disease: Regulators of the interaction between gut microbiota and host immune system. *Seminars in Immunology*, 9(73):101891. DOI: 10.1016/j.smim.2024.101891.

- Raw and processed scientific data used to produce curated scientific data but not included in the final publications will be made available in Zenodo or in available public databases (e.g. plasmid sequences will be deposited in addgene - <https://www.addgene.org/>). The corresponding DOI or accession code will be cited with the published peer-reviewed scientific data. All raw and processed data files will contain a detailed description of how the data is organized and how it was processed. All public deliverables will also be deposited in Zenodo once approved.

To date, the GlycanTrigger project has made **five public deliverables** available on Zenodo, each contributing to the project's dissemination and transparency. These include:

D5.6 Project Website: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14230713>

D6.1 Risk Assessment Analysis: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237364>

D5.1 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237282>

D6.2 Development and Update of the Data Management Plan 1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236988>

D1.1 Definition of the Gut Glycome Map Along the Transition from Health to Inflammation:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237092>

- Educational and Scientific content, when relevant, will also be made available in Zenodo.

The i3S data repository (Network-attached storage – NAS) will be used as online storage during the whole project lifecycle. This allows data to be available when needed online or via VPN when researchers are working off-site. Folders allocated to GlycanTrigger within the i3S institutional drive (NAS) will be only accessed by team members working on the project, to ensure security. This access is allowed only after authentication.

2.3 Making data interoperable

To make data interoperable all data will be written or spoken (videos) in the English language. We will use file formats compliant with available open software applications. The international system of units (SI) will be adopted for all scientific data produced within the Glycan Trigger project.

All data shall be provided in standard and open formats that adhere to both commercial and open software protocols. The primary objective is to promote seamless exchange of data between researchers and institutions.

2.4 Increase data re-use

To optimize metadata descriptions and promote the reuse of data, a standard vocabulary will be employed for metadata description purposes. Additionally, the clarification of licensing information will be included to enhance the potential for data reuse.

Data will be accessible in accordance with Open Licenses to prevent potential issues related to intellectual property rights or access. Once the data is publicly accessible, it will remain so.

Each partner is responsible for ensuring the quality of their respective data. The General Assembly will collaborate closely with the coordinator and the Exploitation and Innovation Managers to provide the necessary tools for dataset description and identification, as well as metafile preparation.

Chapter 3

Other research outputs

3. Other research outputs

In GlycanTrigger, we envision to develop intellectual property and patents related to compositions for a novel nutritional product for personalized prevention of IBD, and corresponding methods of production; as well as a new biomarker and testing method for a non-invasive predictive in vitro diagnostic tool for IBD. We will work with the Knowledge Transfer Office at i3S to conduct diligence, prepare and file such patent applications, as well as to explore commercialization opportunities with corresponding target industries.

Furthermore, we plan to disseminate the project results and outcomes to the wider public through various outreach activities such as lectures, speaking engagements, conferences, interviews and social media campaigns. We will also produce non-technical summaries of the project outcomes and make them available on our project website and social networks of GlycanTrigger. These outputs will maximize the impact and value of our research and ensure that it reaches the widest possible audience. The complete record of the project's communication and dissemination activities will be documented in the four public Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan deliverables (D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, and D5.4) scheduled throughout the project lifecycle.

Chapter 4

Allocation of resources

4. Allocation of resources

There are no immediate costs anticipated to preserve datasets. i3S, the project's coordinator, will be responsible for the data management.

Chapter 5

Data security

5. Data security

Data will be stored and shared within the private collaborative platform. Access to this platform will be restricted through the use of unique usernames and passwords, limited to authorized users. Initially, only the consortium partners and project managers will be granted access to the cloud storage facility where datasets and metadata will be filed. However, the management of stored data may be adjusted in accordance with the inputs provided by the General Assembly.

At i3S, backups are the responsibility of the i3S IT department. Data is protected by an access list and password. i3S has a Data Protection Unit that will provide support to this project, when applicable. The coordinating and partner institutions are responsible for ensuring that backups are performed on a regular basis.

Chapter 6

Ethical aspects

6. Ethical aspects

The GlycanTrigger members will comply with the ethical principles underlining responsible research: the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, Directives of the European Parliament and Council Directive stating the actions related to good practices, and to Directive 98/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 1998 on the legal protection of biotechnological inventions. The consortium partners will comply with the ethical guidelines as laid down by The National Committees for Research Ethics and the EU guidelines for research proposals.

Compliance with the EU GDPR will be secured with the help of i3S and the dedicated Data Protection Officers (DPOs) from the coordinator and partner institutes. Protection and confidentiality of personal data will be guaranteed, as regulated by the different Hospitals and respective countries' laws, as well as with EU legislation. All the information regarding the patient samples will be treated as strictly confidential and pseudonymisation at the source will be required. Procedures to ensure protection and confidentiality of specific GDPR-compliant model documents will be provided by the project coordinator to support the exchange of data between GlycanTrigger partners and the analysis of pools of data from different countries.

All ethical issues related to animal experimentation will be addressed by the i3S and Charité animal ethical committee and authorizations will be obtained from the National Veterinary Authorities. Ethical issues related to pilot clinical trial (WP4) will be managed by LUZ Hospital (GLSMED LH). All the study reporting obligations will be assumed by GLSMED LH (LUZ Hospital).

GlycanTrigger will receive samples (paraffin samples and fresh-frozen tissue samples from CD and HC individuals) and the corresponding clinical/pathological data from the USA and Portugal. The same confidentiality safeguards will be required as stated above: pseudonymisation at the source and strict confidentiality of all the information regarding the patient samples. These safeguards will be clearly stated in the Material and Data Transfer Agreements.

The danger of fraud or falsification of scientific material will be minimised by open and transparent work standards, following the principles of Open Science. No regulated procedures will be started without the approval of the appropriate ethical committees for animal or human research, as required by law. The documents needed for ethical authorization for the use of animals, human samples and the conduction of the clinical study (including patients informed consent and information sheets) will be sent to the EU, prior to the commencement of the relevant parts of the research. Human tissues and blood samples: All samples (paraffin/fresh biopsies, stools and blood) will be collected after written informed consents (obtained by physicians), according to Directives 2004/23/EC and 2001/83/EC.

Chapter 7

Other issues

7. Other issues

GlycanTrigger has a beneficiary from the US and an associated partner from the UK. The consortium is committed to not transferring any personal data and/or material from or to the EU before obtaining the relevant authorisations. Data protection will be safeguarded by clear observance of the European norms and guidelines as stated in Data and Material Transfer Agreements.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

8. Conclusion

This updated version of the DMP for the GlycanTrigger project reflects the practical application and monitoring of data management practices established in the initial plan. Data generation, storage, and sharing have been conducted in alignment with GDPR, Open Science, and FAIR principles since the start of the project. The DMP remains a living document, with updates made as necessary to address any emerging data management needs and ensure continuous compliance.

i3S continues to oversee the DMP's implementation and conducts periodic reviews to ensure the effectiveness and reliability of these data management protocols. This updated version reaffirms GlycanTrigger's commitment to responsible research, adhering to the recommendations of the European Commission and the Data Protection Unit of i3S to maintain high standards in data protection and ethical research conduct.

